

LEGAL PRINCIPLES OF EUTHANASIA: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS BETWEEN DIFFERENT NATIONS

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ABSTRACT

“Every man’s life ends the same way. It is only the details of how he died that distinguish one man from another.”

-Ernest Hemingway.

Euthanasia is one of the most divisive topics in the world, many nations and religious people oppose it since it goes against their religious beliefs. India is no exception. Hinduism contends that the soul is indestructible, and has its roots. A similar belief held by Muslims is that life should only cease at Allah's order and that doing so is evil. Christians also hold that humans shouldn't enter God's domain of life and death since doing so has other unethical implications. However, in some instances, it is asserted in contemporary culture, it is appropriate to give someone the option to choose death. Everyone has the right to life, according to both Article 3 of the 1948 International Declaration of Human Rights and Article 21 of the Indian Constitution. Although it is always up for judicial review and depends on the particular situation, the right to die is identical to other components of the right to life. It's common to hear people refer to euthanasia as "mercy killing" or "good dying." Others argue that in some circumstances, a person should be given the option to choose death rather than being forced to live. Several viewpoints on this issue either disagree with legislations of mercy killing or argue against the recognition of the right to die for particular causes. We have the right to live a decent life and are expected to endure through difficult situations rather than giving up. This study makes an effort to define the issue of euthanasia, examine the legality in various jurisdictions, and conduct a comparative analysis of the legal norms observed in other countries in order to contribute to the development of better legislation. It is urgent that legislation be clearly defined so that people can use it responsibly in the rarest of circumstances and refrain from abusing it.

Keywords: Active Euthanasia, Assisted Suicide Euthanasia, Good Death, Good Dying, Happy Death, Mercy Killing, Passive Euthanasia, Right to Die, Termination of life etc.

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I. INTRODUCTION

“I think those who have a terminal illness and are in great pain should have the right to choose to end their own life, and those that help them should be free from prosecution.”

-Stephen Hawking

The term "euthanasia" derives from the Greek words "eu" and "thanatos," which literally mean "pleasant death" or "easy death" or "happy death." It's also known as "mercy killing" at times. A terminally ill patient's death can be expedited actively or passively to lessen their pain or suffering. Francis Bacon is believed to have coined the phrase in the 17th century to refer to a speedy, painless, and pleasant demise for which the doctor's role and duty was to minimise the physical agony on the patient's body. In their discussion on "Medical Ethics" in England, the House of Lords Select Committee described euthanasia as "a planned intervention done with the stated goal of ending a life to relieve intractable agony. "The European Association of Palliative Care (EPAC) Ethics Task Force clarified in a 2003 discussion on euthanasia that "medicalized killing"—whether non-voluntary (done when the person is unable to consent) or involuntary (done against the person's will)—is a murder when carried out without the person's consent. Euthanasia can only be voluntary, then. As opposed to "active euthanasia," we are here concerned with passive euthanasia. In its ruling in *Aruna Ramachandra Shanbaug vs. Union of India*¹, the Supreme Court of India emphasised the distinction.

According to the eighth edition of Black's Law Dictionary, euthanasia is the deliberate killing or hastening of a person's death who has an incurable illness or condition, especially one that is painful, out of compassion. Euthanasia is described as an act of death designed to relieve a stressful or intolerable state of living in the "Crime and Justice" Britannica. Euthanasia is simply the humane practise of taking someone's life to relieve them of untreatable misery, agony, or pain.

The act of giving a patient medication with the express purpose of ending their life at their request is known as euthanasia². Literally, euthanasia implies putting someone to die without suffering³, especially when they are experiencing unending suffering or when their physical

¹ (2011) 4 SCC 454

² Brody, Baruch. (1998). *Life and Death Decision Making*, New York; Oxford University Press

³ Dr. Parikh, C.K. (2006). *Parikh's Textbook of Medical Jurisprudences, Forensic Medicine and Toxicology*. 6th Edition, Page 1.55. Ne Delhi, CBS Publishers & Distributors

or mental impairment has rendered life meaningless⁴. Euthanasia, also referred to as "mercy killing," is the practise of murdering someone in order to end their painless death or to end their excruciating suffering when their life has become futile and unpleasant. Contemporary euthanasia is limited to patients asking doctors to kill them in order to end their excruciating pain or to end their fatal illnesses. The main objective of euthanasia is to ensure a less painful death for a person who would eventually pass away after going through a lot of pain.

II. EUTHANASIA IN INDIAN LEGAL CONTEXT

Euthanasia is frequently described as compassionate murder. The doctor simply ends the life of an intolerable patient at the patient's request. The debate over euthanasia has a very long history and is rooted in conventional thinking. Nonetheless, it has been perceived in an unexpected manner throughout history. Due to the ongoing advancements in medicine, the concept of euthanasia has recently come under increasing scrutiny (Government of India, 2011). The debate over euthanasia is pressing for modern society due to a small number of other aggravating factors.

One can anticipate that the discussion surrounding the moral acceptability of euthanasia and its decriminalization would intensify by active or covert measures in an effort to relieve the suffering of such patients. It suggests that Francis Bacon used the term to describe a speedy, painless, and pleasant demise in the seventeenth century, for which the doctor had a duty and responsibility to alleviate the patient's physical suffering. "A considering intervention attempted with the express aim of ending a life, to alleviate prolonged suffering"⁵, is the simple act of ending a life that is mentioned. For our evolving societal structures in the twenty-first century, killing, which involves taking intentional action (expecting to terminate or help consummate the life of another person on compassionate grounds), will continue to be a difficulty.

Active euthanasia involves precise acts being taken to stop the suffering of a person who has a terminal illness, by injecting the patient with a fatal drug, like sodium pentothal, which causes the patient to pass away painlessly and go deeply asleep. Hence, active euthanasia is the same as killing someone intentionally. According to the Supreme Court, unless otherwise permitted by law, it is regarded as a felony everywhere in the world (regardless of the

⁴ Nandy, Apurba. (1995) *Principles of Forensic Medicine*, 1st Edition, Page 38. Kolkata New Central Book Agency (P) Ltd.

⁵ *Ibid* at 481

patient's preferences). Under IPC Sections 302 or 304, active euthanasia is forbidden and is regarded as a crime in India as well. A violation of Section 306 of the IPC is physician assisted suicide (abetment to suicide)⁶. However, passive euthanasia, also referred to as "negative euthanasia," has a distinct foundation. It entails withholding medical care or withdrawing life-sustaining equipment, such as antibiotics when a patient would certainly die without them, or removing a patient's heart-lung machine if they are in a coma. Even in the absence of legislation, passive euthanasia is permitted as long as specific guidelines and safety measures are followed⁷. The Supreme Court has stated that the primary distinction between active and passive euthanasia is that in the former, a step is taken to end the patient's life, whereas in the latter, a step that would have preserved the patient's life is not taken. With passive euthanasia, "the doctors are not actively killing somebody; they are simply not saving him," in the words of the erudite Judge in Aruna's case.

The court noted forcefully that while we normally applaud someone who saves another person's life, we do not typically punish someone for doing the opposite. As contrast to active euthanasia, which may or may not be allowed, passive euthanasia is always legal since "you cannot prosecute someone for neglecting to maintain a life," according to the Supreme Court. The House of Lords' famous ruling in the Airedale case⁸, which will be discussed in more detail in the following chapters, was cited by the Supreme Court in rejecting the argument that the distinction was genuine.

There are two other categories of passive euthanasia: voluntary and involuntary. When a patient is put to death voluntarily, their consent is obtained. Due to the patient's state, such as when he is in a coma, consent cannot be obtained in non-voluntary euthanasia. "Although there is no legal impediment in the case of the former, the latter creates various problems, which we shall consider," the Supreme Court stated further. Due to the patient's coma, the Supreme Court was troubled by a case of non-voluntary passive euthanasia.

III. HISTORICAL BACKGROUND

Let's shed some light on the historical context of euthanasia in India before looking at the legal situation. Euthanasia, the right to die, and the option to end one's life are not new ideas or developments in human civilization. In some circumstances, aiding in another person's

⁶ *Ibid* at 481

⁷ (*vide para 39 of SCC in Aruna's case*)

⁸ *Airedale NHS Trust vs. Bland* (1993)1 All ER 821

death or putting them to death was deemed acceptable in ancient Greece and Rome. For instance, infants with serious birth abnormalities were executed at the Greek city of Sparta. In many ancient communities, the elderly's voluntary euthanasia was an accepted practise. Several ancient texts, including the Bible, the Koran, and the Rig-Veda, discuss suicide or self-destruction. The Vedic era of Indian history is replete with innumerable instances of suicides carried out for religious reasons. The Ramayana and the Mahabharata are both replete with accounts of religious suicides.

Hinduism- There are instances from the early days of the Hindu faith in India where monks urged individuals to renounce their bodies (kaya) in order to obtain eternities rewards and advance their quest for God. It is encouraged to urge someone's death if they are suffering⁹ terribly from their illness. The freedom to make one's own decisions¹⁰ is the basis for the right to assert a claim. Everybody enjoys the benefit of the freedom to live their lives as they like and to pursue their own interests. Similar to this, it is stated that everyone should have the choice to end their own life if they feel that it would be better to do so than to remain alive. As a result, he will escape his torturous situation and experience life after death. It can be viewed as a way of delivering healthcare through death. It ends a life that isn't deserving of being lived. For centuries, euthanasia has been practiced. If they received government consent, Athen's residents could get a dose of poison that would let them chose death over suffering. The debate over euthanasia differs from country to country and culture to culture.

The majority of Hindus would contend that a doctor shouldn't consent to euthanasia since doing so would cause the soul and body to be split apart at an unnatural time. The consequence will be bad for the karma of both the doctor and the patient. Some Hindus believe that euthanasia is prohibited because it violates the ahimsa principles (doing no harm). Nonetheless, some Hindus feel that keeping one's moral duty and performing a good deed by assisting in the death of a difficult life fulfils those duties. In their comments on Manu¹¹, Govardana and Kulluka made the observation that, despite Vedic laws prohibiting

⁹ Young K. Euthanasia: Traditional Hindu views and the contemporary debate. In: Coward H, Lippner J, Young K. Hindu ethics: Purity, abortion and euthanasia. New York: State University of New York Press; 1995. p. 16.

¹⁰Young K. Euthanasia: Traditional Hindu views and the contemporary debate. In: Coward H, Lippner J, Young K. Hindu ethics: Purity, abortion and euthanasia. New York: State University of New York Press; 1995. p. 16

¹¹ Manuscripts Commentaries and Digest on folklores

suicide¹², mahaprastha is a journey that ends in death that a man may take if he is terminally ill or experiences a major catastrophe (great departure).

Hinduism has two stances on euthanasia:

1. A person is said to have fulfilled their moral duty by performing a good deed and putting an end to a painful life.
2. By helping to end a life, especially one that was full of suffering, a person tampers with the timing of the cycle of death and rebirth. Euthanasia is considered a dreadful act and anyone who participated in it will inherit the patient's unfinished karma.

Atma-gatha, the Hindu word for suicide, has been noted to contain characteristics of intentionality.¹³ Hinduism¹⁴ forbade the purpose to murder oneself deliberately out of self-interest. Subjectively, evil resulted from ignorance and passion; objectively, evil included the karmic repercussions that slowed down the process of liberation. The Dharmasutras severely forbade suicide in this situation.

Yet, enlightened individuals who consciously chose their way of dying were revered in Hinduism. Hence, on their trek over the Himalayas, the Pandavas celebrated "Mahaparasthana," or the great journey, by travelling as pilgrims and surviving solely on air and water until their bodies gradually decomposed one by one. According to Crawford, some examples of these celebrated demises include fasting, self-immolation, and drowning at sacred sites. Such enlightened people's deaths have never been associated with the widespread idea of suicide in Indian culture. Suicide has traditionally been believed to make future lives more difficult.

Can the above-mentioned Hindu position be applied to the debate over euthanasia? The Indian perspective on life and death deserves special attention in this context. Hinduism views death as a pre-figuration and a metaphor for the complete destruction of the ties that link a person's personality or soul to cosmic impermanence as well as the definitive and unmistakable realization of the ultimate goals of immortality and liberation. Crawford sees a

¹² Laws of Manu, translated by George Buhler, Sacred Books of the East by F. Maxmuller (1967 reprint). Vol. 25, page – 206

¹³ Young K. Euthanasia: Traditional Hindu views and the contemporary debate. In: Coward H, Lippner J, Young K. Hindu ethics: Purity, abortion and euthanasia. New York: State University of New York Press; 1995. p. 16

¹⁴ Crawford SC. Dilemmas of life and death: Hindu ethics in a North American context. Albany, New York, USA: State University of New York Press; 1995. p. 113

"spiritual death" as being akin to a "good death" in the context of Hindu culture, which implies that the person must be at peace and in equilibrium when they pass away. Crawford speculates that in order to ensure such a wonderful death, active euthanasia would not be repugnant to the Indian mentality.

Some authors, however, disagree, contending that "spiritual death," also known as "iccha mrtu," can only take place when the evolved soul voluntarily chooses to depart from the body.¹⁵ It is further claimed that since the evolving soul is at a higher state of consciousness, mental calm cannot be compared to it. Hindus have therefore always maintained a sceptical view of euthanasia, while being less dogmatic than other religions. It has been suggested that the Indian notion of Ahimsa may give rise to a strong opposition to euthanasia. Yet, violence that is unavoidable is not viewed as sinful even within the Gandhian Ahimsa framework. This demonstrates the adaptability of the Indian mind. So, even if it may be a little debatable, the Hindu mind would not consider PAS and euthanasia to be acts of sacrilege.

The same reasoning also holds true for keeping someone on a life support system artificially alive. Yet, using life support system in an interim effort to heal would not be detrimental. Since a conscious dying is the objective, any palliative treatments that lessen mental alertness will be problematic.

Islam- Muslims are against assisted dying. They maintain that all human life is valuable because Allah grants each person life and decides how long they will live. Individuals shouldn't participate in this circumstance. Also, they have faith in two fundamental things:

a) Suicide and euthanasia are not among the justifications for killing in Islam since it believes life is holy. They believe that since Allah declared human life to be holy, we should only take it when it serves the purposes of justice. If someone is killed, it is seen as if the entire population has been slain, barring murder or other serious offences.

b) In the Islamic faith, it is specifically banned to commit suicide or end one's life. Allah is unfailingly compassionate to you.

Christianity- Most Christians oppose euthanasia as well. The arguments typically rest on the claims that God gave us life as a gift and that He created us in His likeness. People go through various life processes that God created, including birth and death. We should honour

¹⁵ Firth S. End-of-life: A Hindu view. *Lancet* 2005;366:682-6

these processes. So, even if someone wants to die, no human has the right to kill an innocent person.

Sikhism- The Guru Granth Sahib and the Sikh Code of Conduct are the main sources from which Sikhs derive their moral ideals.¹⁶ The Sikh Gurus rejected euthanasia and suicide because they believed they were obstructing God's will. They believe that humans should work to change the conditions that karma has put them in, as well as accept suffering without complaining.

There are still opposing opinions on the question of euthanasia's legal standing. Intellectuals debate euthanasia because it needs to be legalised in order to be the focus of a cohesive policy. The reality is that God blessed us with life as a religious gift. The widely held notion is that nobody has the right to take their own life or anybody else's. All major world religions forbid the unnatural end of life. Each person should take on the problems that are presented to them. It is everyone's duty to treat others with respect. Abandoning someone who is in need is against humane thought. Since the dawn of civilised society, we have come to understand that no one should succumb to bad health or agony. We are inspired to help one another and sustain the ideal of unity in the face of difficulty by the concept of a family. Additionally, governments must take action to ensure the welfare of all citizens. It is crucial to honour the sanctity of life in every situation. The tools and resources required to provide assistance to even the most disadvantaged persons should be established by governments. Furthermore, it is illegal for anyone to murder another person. In any circumstance killing is not justified by a person's moral, legal, or ethical principles. In India, like in our society, euthanasia is not approved just at the request of family members since they might be eager to inherit the patient's property.

IV. THE JUDICIAL RESPONSE TO EUTHANASIA IN INDIA

There is no law or regulation that recognizes or authorizes mercy killing in India. The 241st Report of the Law Commission of India, titled "Passive Euthanasia - A Relook," made the suggestion to establish a law on the topic of passive euthanasia and drafted The Medical Treatment of Treatment of Terminally Sick (Protection of Patients and Medical Practitioners)

¹⁶ (The Rehat Maryada)

Bill. The aforementioned Bill was sent to the technical division and Directorate General of Health Services (Dte. GHS) of the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare in June 2014 for review. Meetings called and led by the special director general of the health service were attended by a number of professionals. The Ministry of Health and Family Welfare secretary presided over extra meetings to study the Bill on May 22, 2015, and it was during these meetings that the expert committee ultimately proposed passing legislation outlawing passive euthanasia.

P. RATHINAM N. PATNAIK v. UNION OF INDIA

Euthanasia or mercy killing has long been a topic of legal and social debate due to several terrible scenarios shown in a variety of facts and circumstances. The right to die has occasionally been asserted to fall under the umbrella of the Indian Constitution's article 21 right to a dignified existence. When a patient's dying process results in a protracted delay and intolerable suffering for both the patient and his loved ones, it is suggested that the patient should be permitted to meet his death so that he might be freed from misery and anguish. It is said that the right to life and the right to die with dignity are intertwined. Nevertheless, the Indian Parliament has not yet created a law in this area. The country's highest court has occasionally provided interpretations of the term "euthanasia." The Supreme Court's two-judge panel ruled that attempting suicide is not against the law and that people have the freedom not to live lives that are forced upon them.¹⁷

GIAN KAUR v. STATE OF PUNJAB¹⁸

The constitutional bench of the Supreme Court disagreed with this position.¹⁹ Passive euthanasia is currently permitted in India according to a ruling by the highest court.²⁰

Section 309's constitutional legitimacy was contested, and it was also argued that it violated Article 14 and 21 of the Indian Constitution. It was maintained that the right to speech and expression covers the right to not speak, just as the right to remain alive includes the right to die and terminate one's life. The right to life guaranteed by Article 21 includes the freedom from oppression and coercion. The court upheld section 309 of the Indian Penal Code, 1860

¹⁷ AIR 1994 SC 1844 at 1868

¹⁸ AIR 1994 SC 1844

¹⁹ AIR 1996 SC 946

²⁰ *Common Cause (A Regd. Society) v. Union of India* (2018) 5 SCC 1

beyond the point of no return in order to make our criminal laws more tolerant. The provision was deemed cruel and illogical by the court, and as a result, it is equivalent to punishing a person who is already in anguish due to his refusal to take his own life. The behaviour has no detrimental consequences on society and does not go against morals or government regulations.

In *Airedale N.H.S. Trust v. Bland*²¹, It was emphasised that mercy killing is prohibited under common law. Only legislation can allow for its application. The issue was the removal of life-saving equipment designed to save the doctor's life. Anthony Bland, a supporter of the Liverpool Football Club, visited Hillsborough Stadium during the aforementioned incident and received terrible injuries as a result of which the blood supply to his brain was cut off. He entered a persistent vegetative state as a result of an irreversible brain injury (PVS). The House of Lords ruled that euthanasia is against common law. Only via legislation should it be made legally binding. Only in these situations, where the sufferings of aided suicide are minimal in relation to the sufferings that euthanasia is permitted to alleviate, can it be approved. The sanctity of life is a principle in which the state ought to believe.

Article 21 of the Constitution penalises helping suicide, and it was asserted in the case of Gian Kaur that section 306 violated this provision and that section 309 was affirmed by a two-judge bench in the P. Rathinam ruling. Gian Kaur and her husband Harbans Singh were found guilty of breaking section 306 of the Indian Criminal Code by a trial court. They were punished for aiding Kulwant Kaur's suicide with a six-year prison term and a Rs. 2,000 fine. Section 309 penalises suicide attempts, whereas Section 306 punishes individuals who facilitate suicide. In this instance, the constitutional bench reached a conclusion.

According to the court, article 21 of the Constitution's protection of life does not extend to the right to death. The court ruled that one of the natural rights recognised by Article 21 of the Indian Constitution is the right to life. Contrarily, suicide is an unnatural manner to end a life and is opposed to the concept of the right to life because it has been the foundation of human society from the dawn of civilization. Out of respect and decency, the court refrained from making any analogies between the right to life and the right to death. Although the other puts an end to people's lives, the first provides them a fresh start and some brightness. The right to life and the right to die cannot be compared or justified in light of the conditions listed in

²¹ (1993) 1 All ER 821, HL

article 21. The court ruled that the sanctity of life cannot be diminished by conflating or connecting natural death with artificial death at the conclusion of one's life.

The five-judge constitutional panel found sections 306, 309 of the Indian Criminal Code, 1860 to be constitutional. The Constitutional Bench of the Supreme Court decided that euthanasia and assisted suicide are prohibited in India. The court affirmed the notion that euthanasia should only be made legal by law.

In the case of *Aruna Ramachandra Shanbaug*²², the interested party filed the writ petition on behalf of the victim, who was sexually assaulted by a staff boy in 1973 while working as a nurse in a hospital, 36 years ago. Her brain was unconscious, and she was not cognizant. She was cared after by hospital staff while lying in bed nonstop. The victim's feeding should be stopped, the petitioner contended, and the respondent should be told to do so. After taking into account the physicians' report, the court decided not to permit the victim to stop receiving life-saving treatments or food. Passive euthanasia is the act of discontinuing therapy with the goal of killing the victim. Passive euthanasia also includes not allowing a coma patient to be fed. The court took into account the doctors' assessment and hoped for successful outcomes. The court ruled that legislation is the only way to authorise and spread passive euthanasia throughout India.

In a recent case, *Common Cause Society v. Union of India*²³, the Supreme Court made a decision about euthanasia. According to the petitioner, a registered organisation, the right to a dignified death should be added to the list of fundamental rights in article 21 of the Constitution of India, 1950. In order to ensure that people in poor health or who are terminally ill can sign a document called "My Living Will and Attorney Authorization" that can be presented to a hospital for appropriate action in the event that the executors are admitted with a serious illness that could endanger their lives, the petitioner asks for a declaration and an order to the respondent to adopt appropriate procedures, in consultation with state governments as may be necessary. The right to live with dignity and the right to pass away with dignity, in the eyes of society, go hand in hand.

In instances where a patient's health is continuously deteriorating, a cure is not likely, and the patient is continuously progressing towards death, it was suggested that everyone has the power to choose whether to live or die. It was argued that article 21's complicated and

²² (2011) 4 SCC 454

²³ *Ibid.*

interconnected provision about the right to a dignified death. Because it frees the patient from such an incurable illness in which he is experiencing intolerable torment, passive euthanasia should be made lawful. It provides the sufferer with relief from such pain and trauma. The concepts of a living will and attorney authorisation were also supported.

The patient should be entitled to a pain-free, honourable passing. Nowadays, life is imprisoned or prolonged by the aid of cutting-edge scientific tools and medical care, and the patient must endure great anguish. The individual has the freedom to decide for themselves, including the freedom to accept or reject. Where other options are accessible to him, he has the right to select the course of treatment. He ought to be able to decide for himself. He should have the choice to express his preferences in advance through a living will or through the requests of a surrogate speaking on his behalf in situations when he is unable to communicate due to illness. The surrogate is anticipated to act in the patient's best interest. The right to pass away in dignity was deemed by the court to be an integral aspect of society. Any individual with mental capacity should have the choice to refuse medical treatment, including the withholding of measures that could save their life. The ruling mandated the creation of committees with oversight duties as well.

V. THE LEGAL PRINCIPLES OF EUTHANASIA IN OTHER COUNTRIES

Euthanasia, also known as assisted dying or mercy killing, is a controversial and complex topic in the field of medical ethics and law. Different countries have different legal frameworks and approaches to euthanasia. Here's a comparative analysis of the legal principles of euthanasia in some countries:

SWITZERLAND

Switzerland does not have a specific law on euthanasia, but it allows assisted suicide under certain conditions. The patient must make a voluntary and well-considered request for assisted suicide, and the physician must confirm that the patient is suffering from a terminal or incurable illness and has a clear and settled intention to end their life.

CANADA

Canada legalized euthanasia in 2016, following a landmark Supreme Court ruling. The law allows euthanasia for patients who have a serious and incurable illness, disease, or disability, and whose death is reasonably foreseeable. The patient must make a voluntary and informed

request for euthanasia, and two independent physicians must confirm that the patient meets the eligibility criteria.

UNITED STATES

Euthanasia is illegal in the United States, but some states have legalized assisted suicide. Oregon was the first state to legalize assisted suicide in 1997, followed by Washington, Vermont, California, Colorado, Hawaii, New Jersey, Maine, and New Mexico. The laws vary from state to state but generally require that the patient is a resident of the state, has a terminal illness with a life expectancy of six months or less, and is capable of making an informed decision.

Doctors are allowed to administer lethal doses of drugs to terminally sick patients in five American states. Euthanasia is nonetheless illegal. Although the "help in dying" movement has advanced recently, the issue continues to divide people. Oregon was the first state in America to legalise assisted suicide. With the law's introduction in 1997, terminally ill, mentally competent individuals with less than six months to live have the right to ask a doctor for a prescription for a life-ending medication. A proposition modelled after Oregon's statute was enacted by Washington State more than ten years later. The Vermont legislature also enacted a comparable bill the previous year. In Montana, court rulings made the practise legal. the most recent instance being in New Mexico.

In the United States, the distinction between passive and active euthanasia is still recognised by law. Euthanasia has been declared to be wholly unlawful by the US Supreme Court in the cases *Washington v. Glucksberg*²⁴ and *Vacco v. Quill*²⁵, despite physician assisted dying being permitted in the states of Oregon and Washington under the Oregon Death with Dignity Act of 1997, Washington under the Washington Death with Dignity Act of 2008, and Montana by the State judiciary and not the legislature.

BELGIUM

Belgium legalized euthanasia in 2002, following the Dutch model. The law allows euthanasia for patients who are in a medically futile condition or suffering from unbearable pain or physical or psychological symptoms. The request must be voluntary, well-considered, and

²⁴ 521 US 702 (1997)

²⁵ 521 US 793 (1997)

repeated, and the physician must ensure that the patient is fully informed about their condition and the available treatment options.

On October 25, 2001, the bill allowing euthanasia was approved by a sizable majority in the Belgian Senate. After two days of deliberation, the measure was approved by the lower house of the Belgian parliament on May 16, 2002, with 86 votes in favour, 51 votes against, and 10 abstentions. The statute specified the conditions under which physicians may take the lives of terminally ill people who are suffering intolerably. To be eligible for euthanasia, the applicants must reside in Belgium. Patients who regularly and voluntarily seek having their life removed must be at least 18 years old and make specific demands. Unknown and subject to interpretation is the precise amount of "repeated requests." 11 the 13th of February 2014.

Belgium approved child lethal injection euthanasia by legalising it. By a vote of 86 to 44 with 12 abstentions, the lower house of Parliament approved the proposal that the nation's Senate had already approved. The most drastic euthanasia law expansion ever would allow young children to end their lives with a doctor's help. The age at which a minor may request a lethal injection is unrestricted by law.

NETHERLANDS

The Netherlands was the first country in the world to legalize euthanasia in 2002. The law allows euthanasia for patients who are suffering unbearably and whose death is expected to be within the foreseeable future. The patient must make a voluntary and well-considered request for euthanasia, and the physician must confirm that the patient's suffering is unbearable, the request is voluntary, and there is no alternative to alleviate the suffering. Euthanasia became legal in the Netherlands on April 1, 2002, following the approval of the "Law for the Termination of Life on Request and Assisted Suicide" on April 12, 2001. It is the outcome of a protracted discussion that started in the 1970s and 1980s with a more "understanding" vision for physicians, shaped by case law and built on a number of legislative initiatives. The law of PAS was described as the doctor's prescription of medication for the patient to administer themselves. The law established five requirements for approving an application for euthanasia:

1. The patient's desire must be voluntarily made and carefully thought out.
2. The sufferer should endure severe and hopeless anguish.

3. The patient will be advised of their circumstances and outlook.
4. There are no practical alternatives that are available.
5. Also, a second doctor should be consulted, and euthanasia should be carried out with the appropriate medical care and attention. Two independent doctors, including at least one psychiatrist, must have been consulted when a mentally ill patient requests euthanasia.

In the Netherlands, euthanasia is governed by the "Termination of Life on Request and Assisted Suicide (Review Procedures) Act," passed in 2002. It states that physician-assisted suicide and euthanasia are not punishable crimes if the accompanying physician acts with the requirements of due care. In extremely rare situations and under very precise conditions, it permits the legalisation of euthanasia and physician-assisted suicide. According to the penal code of the Netherlands, aiding in suicide carries a three-year prison sentence or fine in addition to a twelve-year prison sentence for killing someone at their behest. However, if all of the following conditions are satisfied, the legislation allows a medical review board to stop legal proceedings against doctors who performed euthanasia:

1. There is no hope for the patient's excruciating anguish to be relieved.
2. The patient must freely and repeatedly ask to be put to sleep (the request cannot be granted when under the influence of others, psychological illness, or drugs).
3. To confirm the facts, at least one additional impartial doctor must be consulted.
4. The death must be brought about by the patient or physician in a way that is medically required, in which case the physician must be present.
5. There is a patient that is at least 12 years old (patients between 12 and 16 years of age require the consent of their parents).

UK- ENGLAND

Non-voluntary euthanasia for individuals in a persistent vegetative state was approved in England by the House of Lords in the *Airedale NHS Trust v. Bland*²⁶ decision. It was a case involving a doctor withdrawing artificial life-supporting measures. It was ruled that it would

²⁶ 1993(1) All ER 821 (HL)

be illegal to treat an adult who is conscious and of sound mind without his consent. Such a person is entirely free to choose not to receive treatment, even if doing so will cause him to pass away. It was further decided that in cases where a person lost consciousness due to an accident or another event and was unable to give or withhold consent to medical care, medical professionals were allowed to administer treatment if they believed it to be in the best interests of the unconscious patient. It is unlawful to perform such actions, regardless of how severely the patient may be suffering, even if the doctor is acting out of compassion. In this case, Anthony Bland should be permitted to pass away, according to all of the House of Lords justices.

The law is now fairly well established that, in the case of incompetent patients, if the doctors act on the basis of their expert medical judgement and remove the artificial life support system if doing so is in the patient's best interest, the said act cannot be regarded as a crime. This is because the Airedale case, decided by the House of Lords, was followed in a number of cases in the United Kingdom. Who will determine the patient's best interests when he is in a chronic vegetative state, however, is still an open subject (PVS)

Despite the fact that there have been numerous court rulings on this issue in the United States of America, frequently using different strategies. Justice Cardozo made the following observation while serving on the Court of Appeals for the State of New York: "Every human being of adult years and sound mind has the right to determine what shall be done with his or her own body, and a surgeon who performs an operation without his or her patient's consent commits an assault, for which he or she is liable in damages."²⁷

Overall, the legal principles of euthanasia vary widely across countries, reflecting different cultural, ethical, and religious values. However, the common themes across these countries include the importance of patient autonomy, informed consent, and the involvement of medical professionals in the decision-making process.

RUSSIA

Euthanasia, the practice of intentionally ending a life in order to relieve suffering, is a highly controversial issue around the world. While some countries have legalized euthanasia in certain circumstances, others have strict laws against it. In Russia, euthanasia is illegal and is considered a criminal offense. The Russian Government's position on euthanasia is clear; it is

²⁷ *Schloendorff v. Society of New York Hospital*, 211 N.Y. 125, 129-30, 105 N.E. 92, 93 (1914)

strictly forbidden. The Russian Criminal Code states that “causing a person’s death by prior agreement or with his consent” is punishable by imprisonment for a term of up to 10 years. This means that anyone who performs euthanasia, assists in it, or even discusses it with a patient can be charged with a criminal offense. One of the main reasons why euthanasia is illegal in Russia is due to the country’s strong religious beliefs. The Russian Orthodox Church, which is the dominant religion in the country, strongly opposes euthanasia, arguing that it goes against the sanctity of life. The Government has also cited concerns that legalizing euthanasia could lead to abuse and the exploitation of vulnerable individuals.

Another reason why euthanasia is illegal in Russia is due to the lack of adequate palliative care services. Palliative care is a type of medical care that focuses on relieving pain and other symptoms of serious illness, with the goal of improving the quality of life for patients and their families. In Russia, palliative care services are limited, and many patients suffer from untreated pain and other symptoms, leading some to consider euthanasia as a last resort. Despite the strict laws against euthanasia in Russia, there have been cases where patients have sought out euthanasia in other countries. For example, in 2015, a Russian woman suffering from cancer traveled to Switzerland to receive assisted suicide, which is legal in that country. This case sparked a debate in Russia about the need to legalize euthanasia or improve palliative care services.

The insights of euthanasia law in Russia reveal a complex issue that is deeply rooted in the country’s religious beliefs and concerns about patient safety. While some argue that legalizing euthanasia could provide a humane option for patients suffering from terminal illness, others believe that it could lead to abuse and the exploitation of vulnerable individuals. Ultimately, the decision on whether to legalize euthanasia in Russia will depend on a wide range of factors, including public opinion, medical ethics and Government policy.

VI. INTERNATIONAL SITUATION OVER EUTHANASIA

In accordance with international humanitarian law, there is no "right to die." Any human rights document's common meaning does not imply the existence of a "right to a good death." Contrarily, states are urged in human rights declarations to safeguard and preserve everyone's life. Only four of the 193 members of the United Nations (UN) have legalised euthanasia (the Netherlands, Belgium, Luxembourg, and Canada). Despite the fact that the issue is still very

contentious, many legislative bodies have opted against it²⁸. The 2006 Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities was adopted by the United Nations as an international convention to uphold human rights and dignity. According to a UN international treaty, "States Parties shall take all appropriate steps to ensure that persons with disabilities have the same right to the effective enjoyment of the right to life as other persons."²⁹ According to Article 6(1) of the 1966 International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, every human being has an intrinsic right to life (ICCPR). No one's life may be taken against their will. Article 6 (1) of the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) states that every child has an intrinsic right to life and Article 7 of the ICCPR, states that people should be protected from inhuman or degrading treatment.

In 2001, Holland legalized assisted suicide. The Dutch Parliament passed the Termination of Life on Request and Assisted Suicide (Review of Procedures) Act, 2001, which formalizes a previous judicial decision to relax the law against euthanasia and assisted suicide. According to the Act, euthanasia and doctor-assisted suicide are only permissible if the patient agrees to it and a doctor is there to supervise it.³⁰ Belgium passed the Belgian Act on Euthanasia on May 28, 2002. In accordance with Belgian legislation, physicians were permitted to assist in the killing of terminally ill patients who expressed a desire to die sooner. Euthanasia is only permitted under very specific situations and guidelines set forth by Belgian law. The patient must submit a written request. If the patient is unable to create the paperwork themselves, they choose a person to do it on their behalf. When a doctor confirms that a patient has reached adulthood, is legally capable, aware of making requests, and makes requests while experiencing constant, intolerable physical pain as a result of incurable suffering brought on by sickness or accident, the doctor does not violate the law. There must not be a workable answer. The patient may choose someone else to submit the request on his behalf if he is unable to do so himself. This person must be at least 18 years old and have no financial stake in the patient's demise. Any competent person, however, may draught advance instructions to be conveyed to doctors regarding unconscious patients suffer from an accident or an incurable ailment in cases where no one is able to make request.³¹

²⁸ Available at: <https://adflegal.blob.core.windows.net/international-content/docs/-dated on 29/08/2021>

²⁹ Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities , 2006, art.10.

³⁰ Available at : <https://associatie.kuleuven.be/p/flandershealthcare/tourofflanders/belgian-law-oneuthanasia.pdf>, (last visited on Aug.25, 2021).

³¹ Available at : <https://associatie.kuleuven.be/p/flandershealthcare/tourofflanders/belgian-law-oneuthanasia.pdf>, (last visited on Aug.25, 2021).

With the passage of the law on March 16, 2009, Luxembourg became the third nation to decriminalize assisted suicide. Those who are terminally sick will be permitted to end their lives with the agreement of two physicians and a group of specialists. In Canada, if a terminal illness has progressed to the point where natural death is "reasonably foreseeable," persons over the age of 18 who have it are eligible for "physician aided dying," often known as voluntary active euthanasia. The position in Canada altered following the Supreme Court of Canada's decision in *Cartar v. Canada (Attorney General)* (Attorney General). Euthanasia is not allowed in either China or Hong Kong as it goes against its traditional moral ideals. It is the equivalent of murder under Chinese law as it stands. In the United Kingdom, assisted suicide is forbidden. Anyone who is caught encouraging someone to commit suicide will be breaking the law, which carries a maximum 14-year prison sentence. The House of Lords ruled that the European Convention's protection of the right to life and other human rights, which is enforced in England under the Human Rights Act of 1998, has not had an effect on the aforementioned law. And, the convention does not require a state to legalize assisted suicide. Director of Public Prosecutions, however, disagreed with this conclusion.³²

In Germany, active euthanasia is authorized while passive euthanasia is not. It is not a criminal act, for a doctor to stop performing life-saving procedures at a patient's written request. While active euthanasia is prohibited in the United States (US), it is not. Only a few States, such as Oregon, Washington, and Montana, have legalized some form of physician assisted suicide. Physician-assisted suicide and euthanasia have been distinguished from one another. Only self-assisted suicide is legal in both Oregon and Washington. Outside of the legal restrictions, aiding someone in dying or helping them commit suicide by a physician is still a crime. In the US, a doctor can only turn off life support at a patient's request. The doctor's evaluation simply takes into account the patient's desire to end his life.

VII. SUGESSATION

The researcher thinks that legalization and protection of passive euthanasia are necessary. Euthanasia must, however, be legalized along with a number of clear and defined restrictions that must be carefully planned after taking into account its implications for both public policy and individual rights. Furthermore, legalizing active euthanasia should only apply to voluntary euthanasia. The patients themselves should sign a form indicating their desire for

³² *Supra* note 6.

euthanasia. However, euthanasia performed against the patient's will or without his or her consent should continue to be considered illegal. Non-voluntary euthanasia is performed when the patient is unable to make the decision for themselves. Using this concept, discrimination and inappropriate euthanasia would be avoided. Only in extreme cases, after consulting with doctors and, if necessary, psychiatrists, should euthanasia be considered. Finally, before choosing euthanasia, it is important to promote and evaluate alternatives like palliative care. The topic of euthanasia is extremely sensitive and emotional, which leads to discussion and mistakes. It doesn't reflect a clear organization of concepts and definitions, despite its constant presence in public media and academic writing. More often than not, killing peaceful arguments turn out to be poorly designed and inadequate, leading to disappointment instead of solutions. One might anticipate that the conversation around great passing will continue to be a real social and legal problem because it is an existential, genuinely delicate, and ethically contested conversation. The fundamental conflict is that, while the right to life must be firmly guaranteed, independence and individual rights must be advanced in order for a person to decide for himself or herself how to live and die. Consideration should be given to the answers to the many questions that are left unanswered and lead to ambiguity. A clear regulation on this touchy subject is desperately needed right now, given the persisting philosophy, culture, and normal and physical sensitivity of our nation, where religion is the essential and unavoidable source of existence.

VIII. CONCLUSION

New laws are being codified every day as a result of the need to adapt the law as civilization develops, steadily as new areas of human rights are created, and as a result, new features of the law. Prior to the advent of due process of law, the majority of legal principles were founded on custom rather than being codified. New methods and procedures are developed as a result of scientific and technological progress. New claims are recognized as new faculties of life develop, and at the same time, these claims are given the status of statutory rights. There are additional situations where claims are recognized as rights in the absence of legislation with the aid of prior judicial rulings. For instance, passive euthanasia is one of the situations in which the right is acknowledged by a legal ruling. It is appropriate to applaud the Supreme Court's judgement. Euthanasia should be permitted with the appropriate care and consideration since the doctor or doctors who are meant to do it may be under pressure.

The virtuous species of this cosmos is the human. He is this God's finest creation. The sacredness of life ought to be upheld. A safe and healthy living must be provided by the government. But life has also grown incredibly difficult in today's world. Humans suffer greatly from a variety of ailments. In every sector, scientific developments and methods have increased. Also, these advancements have had an effect on medical study and ultimately, human lives. People profit from the use of newly developed medical therapies in that they not only have access to life-preserving medications when they would otherwise have to wait their entire lives for natural death, but also from having their lives prolonged. Healthy living is the priceless jewelry of life. With health, one can enjoy life. The ability to live a dignified life, which includes the freedom to make decisions for oneself and to reject them, is a benefit to the individual. Patients should be permitted to decline treatment when their health is in such horrible form and they are in such severe agony that there are no longer any hopes for them to recover or live. Alternatively, if he had previously said that he would like to accomplish something but is no longer able to; his wish should be taken into account. Occasionally, a patient may decide to undergo euthanasia because of the conditions in his life. He should be examined and cared for by a psychiatrist in this case to determine whether he is depressed or not. Every human being deserves the right to pass away with dignity, whether they are healthy or afflicted with a deadly illness. The availability and protection of human rights are related to the problem.

Article 21 of the Indian Constitution states that in order to be protected from exploitation, a person's right to a dignified death must be. Passive euthanasia should be performed on the patient with the necessary caution and care. Since India's society is undereducated and has a high crime rate, granting active euthanasia may not be appropriate in the current climate, protecting the patient's security and best interests.

In a country like India where family and any other beneficiary may be interested in getting the property and assets of patients in inheritance, it is the obligation of the government to conduct it following a proper investigation and the confirmation of doctors and their conclusions. Property conflicts are highly widespread in India, where people frequently kill people to inherit their property or falsify legal documents in civil cases such wills, powers of solicitor, and other legal documents. Property is one of the primary motivators of crime and fraud in society. Due to the population boom and inadequate economic resources, people are very readily persuaded to commit crimes and wrongdoing in our country, where corruption is

also at an all-time high. They don't have any obligations to care for their families or for the upbringing of their kids. These factors make it possible for them to be easily persuaded to participate in the commission of a crime.

To grant the same from an Indian perspective, the law makers must examine the whole context and the socio-legal circumstances. The Supreme Court has taken into account the underlying motivations of those who are accountable for not taking active euthanasia into consideration. The Indian Supreme Court has approved passive euthanasia and ordered the creation of legislation outlining its restrictions. The top court also supported the creation of a commission to act as a watchdog over the execution of mercy killings. The court's decision is really admirable since it sheds light on the situation. The patient's pain and quiet passing away were given priority by the supreme court, who also approved of the same. The right to die with dignity is a positive extension of the right to life under Article 21 of the Constitution. Even while the legalization of passive euthanasia should be commended, it is the duty of the Parliament to draught the relevant legislation and the rules for its best-possible implementation. It would aid in clarifying the situation.

Regardless of geography or religious affiliation, the concept of life is revered and regarded as sublime and sacred by all civilizations and faiths. Euthanasia is not considered to be a moral act or a person's right by many religious groups since they hold the view that life, which has been bestowed upon one, must be honored. As a result, those who oppose active euthanasia emphasize the sanctity of life at all costs (which is primarily supported by arguments from the Christian and Islamic religions, which forbid any form of suicide), while those who support it believe that doctors have a moral obligation to end the suffering of a terminally ill patient while also emphasizing strong individual autonomy in matters of life and death. Hence, euthanasia can be morally supported or opposed while still taking into account the patient's welfare, freedom, and necessities of life.

Euthanasia has a huge negative effect on society as a whole. It directly impacts not just the person getting euthanasia but also every member of their family, friend, and acquaintance. It has an impact on how doctors perform their jobs as well as how people generally interpret and perceive death.

In the last few decades, euthanasia has started to become legal. There is little doubt that the increasing value placed on individualism in society is one of the causes of euthanasia. There

appears to be either a complete lack of awareness or a denial that this kind of individuality can jeopardize the social and cultural fabric, the intangible foundation upon which society is built. The community will inevitably be destroyed by individualism that is unhindered by at least care or perhaps the duty to defend and promote the community. Euthanasia would therefore be legalized even if it is a product of unchecked individualism, at least in terms of the balance between the individual and the community.

At some point, society won't be able to protect the most defenseless from abuse, and doctors will start acting more like killers than healers. The dehumanization of doctors will alter how people view them, which will affect the doctor-patient relationship as well as the trust and morals that underpin it.

Euthanasia also significantly affects how we view death itself. Euthanasia is a notion that suggests using death to end human suffering. When death is the solution, we as humans lose the chance to push ourselves further, work harder, and give these individuals reason to believe. Accepting assisted suicide is a statement that certain lives are not worth living and should be ended, depending on the situation.

Euthanasia may alleviate a patient's suffering, but it paints a bleak and depressing picture for the rest of society. Being able to die is a concern because, for those with trauma, depression, or other mental illnesses, dying or committing suicide might be an option even when it is not necessary. Suicide being illegal will not be able to modify this thinking or put a stop to it.

Euthanasia not being a public policy has also been defended in a number of ways. First off, in most nations, legalizing euthanasia will be based on hazy criteria that weigh the costs and advantages of doing so.

Another potential foundation for this approach is substituted judgement, which gives the surrogate decision-maker the authority to euthanize people they determine to be incompetent. This approach would be relied on a review of the patient's values, which might be unreliable in some circumstances. Moreover, such vague and ambiguous techniques may be abused to target members of particular groups, a practice known as discriminatory euthanasia. My survey's findings provide greater credence to this assertion. More over half of the survey participants think that prejudice could result from the legalization of euthanasia.

IX. RECOMMENDATIONS

The practice of passive euthanasia, which is permitted in many other countries, will also be acknowledged legally in our country with certain protections, in accordance with the recommendations made by India's 17th Law Commission and decisions made by the Supreme Court in the case of Aruna Ramachandra. From a legal and constitutional standpoint, it is not problematic.

As long as the doctor is satisfied that the patient has made a "informed decision" based on the free exercise of his or her will, the patient has the right to demand that no invasive medical treatment—including artificial life support or treatment—be given. This decision is binding on the doctors and hospitals caring for the patient. The same standards will be used for minors over the age of 16, as long as they have stated a desire to forego the treatment and one of their parents and the significant spouse have both granted their agreement.

An incompetent patient, such as one who is in an incurable coma or a chronic vegetative state, or a competent patient who has not made a "informed decision," cannot be forced to accept the doctor's or a patient's relative's decision to discontinue medical care. To stop or delay life-sustaining treatment, the relevant doctors, hospital administration, or concerned family members must first obtain High Court approval.

The Law Commission's proposals in its 196th report differ slightly in this regard. An authorization clause to petition the High Court was proposed by the Law Commission. After hearing from three medical experts and taking into account the patient's family's pleas, the High Court will issue its ruling. The Supreme Court will select the best option for the patient in its capacity as *parens patriae*. The new laws safeguard medical practitioners and others from legal action when they follow a competent patient's preferences or a High Court order. A competent patient who is terminally ill and refuses medical treatment is therefore not regarded as having breached any laws.

The process for creating panels has been laid up generally in accordance with the suggestions made by the 17th Law Commission. Prior to becoming ill, the patient gave a lawful advance medical directive. Even if medical treatment has been withheld or stopped in accordance with the aforementioned standards, both competent and incompetent patients are eligible for palliative care.

Governments must develop plans that are reasonably priced, for palliative care for terminally ill people who are experiencing unrelenting misery. The Medical Council of India must publish guidelines for the withholding or withdrawal of medical care from competent or incompetent individuals who are afflicted with terminal illnesses. The Medical Treatment of Terminally Ill Patients (Protection of Patients and Medical Practitioners) Bill, 2006, which was drafted by the 17th Law Commission in the 196th Report, has been modified in light of this. In essence, the new Bill combines the earlier Law Commission recommendations with the rulings and recommendations made by the Supreme Court in the Aruna Ramachandra case.

Furthermore, the Guidelines provided by the SC under the 2018 case has undergone modifications recently; in the 2023 report SC simplified the rules on accessing passive euthanasia. The three tiered system consisting of doctor, patient's family and judicial Magistrate has been reduced to two. Further, stated that the approval of magistrate is no more required for the two tiered process introduced in 2018 guidelines for withdrawing life support. These changes not only make the guidelines simpler but also remove legal constraints of the hospitals dealing with such cases. However, the plot twist is that, we are dealing with an issue of ending a life which we cannot bring it back once the process begins and simplifying such process makes it easier to avail and more accessible but we must not take it lightly. Therefore, a proper legislation is still in need for the hour and for the long run.

The Government must ensure that the doctors do not neglect on evaluating the patient's mental capacity, emotional state and social circumstances, to confirm that the request is not due to depression, anxiety, or another reversible factor. Ensuring Palliative care, pain management and psychological support are available and accessible to all patients, regardless of their decision. Patients should have the right to optimal symptom control and quality of life and must not be coerced or pressured to choose euthanasia due to inadequate or unavailable care. Such equipment needed for palliative care must be the first primary goal to be made available.

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